

Synthesis, Characterisation and Screening of some New Hydrazides and 2-Aryl-5-(8'-methoxycoumarin-3'-yl)-1,3,4-oxadiazoles as Antibacterial Agents

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Manuscript received 31 October 1994, revised 5 May 1995, accepted 13 September 1995

A large number of substituted hydrazides including heterocyclic compounds having five- or six-membered rings possess various biological activities¹. Also substitution of oxadiazole with 4-methyl-7-coumarinyloxy moiety shows remarkable activity against bacteria². With this view, we report herein the synthesis of some new hydrazides of coumarin by two different approaches to study the biological profile of these compounds. Thus, the acid chloride of 3-carboxy-8-methoxycoumarin was condensed with various substituted benzhydrazides to yield some new oxadiazoles. The second approach was to condense the parent acids with substituted benzhydrazides in the presence of POCl₃.

Some of the oxadiazoles (2) were screened for antimicrobial activity using cup-plate method³ at 100 and 500

ppm concentration against strains of *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *S. typhosa* and *S. albus* using ampicillin as control. The compounds showing moderate activity are 2f against *E. coli*, 2f and g against *S. aureus* at 100 ppm dose, and 2a, b, f and g against *E. coli*, 2f, g against *S. aureus* and 2d, f against *S. typhosa* at 500 ppm dose. The hydrazides (1a-l) did not show any activity at the above mentioned concentrations.

Experimental

All m.ps. are uncorrected. Microanalysis of the compounds were performed on a Coleman 33 instrument. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu 408 spectrophotometer, nmr spectra on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as the internal standard and mass spectra on a Hewlett-Packard 5985 instrument at 70 eV. All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

1-Aryl-4-(8'-methoxy-3'-coumarinyl)-2,3-diaza-1,4-dioxobutane (1a-n): The acid chloride was prepared by refluxing 3-carboxy-8-methoxycoumarin with thionyl chloride in dry benzene until the solution was clear. The excess of thionyl chloride and benzene were then distilled off. A mixture of the acid chloride (0.01 mol) and various aryl hydrazides (0.01 mol) was stirred in ether for 3-4 h. The resulting solids were crystallised from appropriate solvents (yields 55-70%): ν_{\max} 3 200-3 200 (NH), 1 720-1 710 (δ -lactone), 1 640-1 620 (CONH), 1 600 cm⁻¹ (aryl); 1a, m.p. 248° (DMF-H₂O), δ (CF₃COOH) 2.01 (3H, s, Ph-CH₃), 3.7 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.5-7.0 (7H, m, ArH), 8.76 (1H, s, C₄-H of coumarin ring), *m/z* 352 (M⁺), 203 (M⁺-C₈H₉N₂O), 91 (M⁺-C₁₂H₉N₂O₅) (M⁺-C₁₂H₉N₂O₄, base peak); 1b, m.p. 253° (DMF-H₂O); c, 221° (DMF-H₂O); d, 246° (DMF-H₂O); e, 274° (DMF); f, 268° (DMF-H₂O); g, 268° (DMF); h, 306° (DMF-H₂O); i, 288° (DMF-H₂O); j, 306° (DMF-H₂O); k, 304° (DMF); l, 300° (DMF); m, 264° (DMF-H₂O); n, 165° (DMF-H₂O).

2-Aryl-5-(8'-methoxy-3'-coumarinyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (2a-l). **Method 1**: 1-Aryl-4-(8'-methoxy-3'-coumarinyl)-2,3-diaza-1,4-dioxobutane (0.01 mol) was heated on a steam-bath for 5 h in POCl₃ (0.05 mol, excess), which also worked as the solvent. The reaction mixture was then poured in ice-cold water and the resulting solid was crystallised from appropriate solvent. **Method 2**: A mixture of 3-carboxy-8-methylcoumarin (0.01 mol), substituted-benzhydrazides (0.01 mol) and POCl₃ (0.05 mol, excess) was heated for 5 h on a steam-bath. The reaction mixture was

1a-n

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|---|--|
| 1a; R = H, R ₁ = <i>m</i> -CH ₃ | h; R = H, R ₁ = <i>o</i> -NO ₂ |
| b; R = H, R ₁ = <i>p</i> -CH ₃ | i; R = H, R ₁ = <i>m</i> -NO ₂ |
| c; R = H, R ₁ = <i>m</i> -OCH ₃ | j; R = H, R ₁ = <i>p</i> -NO ₂ |
| d; R = H, R ₁ = <i>p</i> -OCH ₃ | k; R [*] = H, R ₁ = <i>p</i> -OH |
| e; R = H, R ₁ = <i>o</i> -Cl | l; R = H, R ₁ = <i>p</i> -NH ₂ |
| f; R = Br, R ₁ = <i>p</i> -Cl | m, R = Br, R ₁ = <i>p</i> -Cl |
| g; R = H, R ₁ = <i>m</i> -Br | n; R = Br, R ₁ = 3-Br |

2a-l

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|---|---|
| 2a; R = H, R ₁ = <i>m</i> -NO ₂ | g, R = H, R ₁ = <i>m</i> -OCH ₃ |
| b; R = H, R ₁ = <i>p</i> -NO ₂ | h; R = H, R ₁ = <i>p</i> -NH ₂ |
| c; R = Br, R ₁ = <i>p</i> -NO ₂ | i, R = H, R ₁ = <i>m</i> -CH ₃ |
| d; R = H, R ₁ = <i>o</i> -Cl | j; R = H, R ₁ = <i>p</i> -CH ₃ |
| e, R = Br, R ₁ = <i>p</i> -Cl | k; R = H, R ₁ = <i>o</i> -NO ₂ |
| f, R = Br, R ₁ = <i>m</i> -Br | l, R = H, R ₁ = <i>p</i> -OH |

then poured in ice-cold water and the resulting solid was crystallised from appropriate solvent (yields 55–70%) : ν_{\max} 1 750–1 720 (δ -lactone), 1 675 (C=N), 1 600 cm^{-1} (aromatic ring); 2a, m.p. 290° (DMF-H₂O); b, 300° (DMF); c, 300° (DMF); d, 175° (DMF-H₂O); e, 254° (DMF-H₂O), δ (CF₃COOH) 3.7 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.9–6.9 (6H, m, ArH), 9.0 (1H, s, C₄-H coumarin ring); f, 320° (DMF); g, 225° (DMF-H₂O); h, 310° (DMF); i, 224° (DMF-H₂O); j, 264° (DMF-H₂O); k, 270° (DMF-H₂O), m/z 365 (M⁺), 203 (base peak), M⁺- C₇H₄N₃O₂), 104 (M⁺- C₁₁H₇N₃O₅); l, 300° (DMF), δ 2.13 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.72 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.7–7.1 (7H, m, ArH), 8.81 (1H, s, C-4'-H).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. P. K. Bhattacharya, Chemistry Department, M. S. University of Baroda for his

interest in the work, to Dr. Madhava Rao, for microanalysis and pmr spectra, to Sushila Amin, for ir spectra, to IPCL for mass spectra and to Prof. K. K. Rao, Head of Microbiology Department, M. S. University of Baroda, for biological screening.

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